

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14176004

Accessing Of Causes Of Dropout Among Girls In Senior Secondary School In Sokoto State: Sustainable Solution

¹Yusuf Aishatu & Muhammad Bello Waziri²

¹Department of Educational Management
Shehu Shagari University of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria
aishayusuf3@gmail.com/ +2348036251063

²Department of Educational management
Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria
bellowaziri24@gmail.com/08065779651

ABSTRACT

This study will assess causes of dropout among girls in senior secondary schools in Sokoto State. The problem of girls dropping out of school in the state brings a shortfall of women participation in development issues in the state an educated girl has the ability to make a modern home and other ways of life necessary for human survival. Three research objective ate raise psychological factor, physical factor and educational factor as they contribute to dropout of girls in senior secondary school in the state. The composition of population is 6745and simple random sampling technique is going to be used to select the respondent. The instrument to be use is structured questionnaire named causes of dropout among senior secondary school girls (CDSSGQ). The data to be obtained will be analyzed using mean and standard deviation. All analysis will be done using SPSS application.

Keywords: Dropout, Secondary school, Girls

INTRODUCTION

Education is a vital tool for national development and individual empowerment, significantly contributing to societal progress in Sokoto State, however, the high dropout rate among senior secondary school girls present a major obstacle. This issue not only limit individual potential but also affect broader community social and economic growth. Understanding the causes of this dropout phenomenon is essential for creating effective solutions. Several interrelated factors contribute to dropout rate among girls in sokoto state cultural norms such as traditional belief about gender roles, often discourage girls from pursuing education. Additionally, economic challenges, including poverty and the of girls to contribute to house hold income further exacerbate the problem. Early marriage, which are prerace in the region also significantly impact girls ability to continue their education. The complexity of these issues requires a nuanced approach to understand the specific challenges faced by girls in both urban and rural areas of sokoto state. While previous research has primary focused on urban settings, rural communities experience distinct barriers that are often overlooked. These include limited access to schools, inadequate educational resource and social pressure that priorities marriage over education. In exploring the psychological, physical and educational factors influencing girls dropout rate, this study aims to fill the existing research gap. Psychological factors such as low self-esteem and lack of motivation can discourage girls from continuing their education. Physical factors include inadequate school infrastructure and long distance to school also play a role. Educational factors such teaching quality and curriculum relevance further impact retention rate. Addressing these

issues is critical for fostering gender quality and improving educational outcomes in Sokoto State by identifying the root cause of dropout among senior secondary girls, this study seek to inform policy and programmatic interventions that support girls education. Ultimately, empowerment girls education will contribute to the overall development of their communities, promoting social stability and economic growth.

Problem statement/justification

The problems facing Nigerian educational system cannot be over generalized because of the diversity characterizing its history which makes some problems peculiar to certain States. In Sokoto State, variations in girls' educational participation within the various socio-economic states is quite significant, girls education deserves a special attention. Thus, the problem of female students dropout in Sokoto seems worth stressing The 2005 National School Census (NSC), revealed that there are large geographical and gender disparities between South and Northern. Nigeria partly due to parental socio-economic support, cultural, religious and educational factors. Female net enrolment ratios (NER) in some states in the South are as high as 70%, while, some in the North are as low as 10%.(National school census report 2005)

Moreover, socio-economic status, cultural, traditional practice and religious belief of the parent are some of the parental factors affecting the system. Some parents who have a very low socio-economic support to the extent that they are always struggling for their survival talk less of the education of their daughters. Traditionally. they attached less importance to the education of girls therefore, any attempt to contribute to its development is rendered useless. Ajaja (2012), was quoted to have said that "Globally, reasons why student dropout from school can be categorized into Four Clusters. These include, School related, Job related, Family related and Community related. His finding was supported by Freudenberg and Ruglls (2007) who identified parental occupation, parent's socio-economic support and parent's educational background and among Twenty Four factors under family cluster that leads to student dropout. Misperception of the real teaching of Islam about female education also leads them to show negative attitudes in the education of their daughter. These factors however become Problem that needs to be investigated in Sokoto State, the motive behind girl's dropout of school and it increasing in the society. This has also becomes an African problem that needs to further be investigated; society with a view to finding ways in order to address it.

The problem of this study is to assess the causes of dropout among Senior Secondary School Girls in Sokoto State. An educated Girl has the ability to make a modem home, maintain a higher standard of cleanliness and attractive surroundings. Socialize with her children, maiming stable marriage and other ways of life necessary for human survival. She develops essential life skills, including self-confidence, ability to participate effectively effect in societal welfares and protect herself from sexual exploitation and pressure for early marriage. It appears that, society today most especially northern Nigeria and Sokoto State in particular as a result of dropout from senior secondary school one (SSI) in Sokoto State there is a shortfall of women participation in education and other development issue in the state. There is a great concern to our education planners, parent and society in general to consider the importance of girl's education with respect to increase in demand for female manpower especially in the area that that is regarded traditionally for women.

Objective of the study

The object of the research are as follows:

1. To find out psychological factors responsible for girls dropout in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
2. To investigate physical factors contributing to girls dropout in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Research questions

The following research questions helped to guide the study: -

1. What are the psychological factors contributing to girls dropout in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?
2. What are the physical factors contributing to girls dropout in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?

Scope and delimitation of the study

This study was designed to cover all girls in senior secondary schools one (SS1) in Sokoto state but due to time factor the researcher limited it to two educational zone in the state which comprises

Significance of the study

- it is helped that the finding of the study would be helpful to the government, stakeholders, community, teachers and school administrators as teachers should create good relationship and friendly environment for students to feel they are at home, by so doing,
- it will help in controlling student emotional, phobia and psychological problem and they will feel free to speak out the fear in them.
- Also sex education should include in school curricula and should be taught by specialist
- it help in educating girls on danger involved in social interaction that may lead to unwanted pregnancy and give them a clear picture in difficulties in becoming a teenage mothers.
- it help in educating girls on danger involved in social interaction that may lead to unwanted pregnancy and give them a clear picture in difficulties in becoming a teenage mothers.

Review of Related Literature

There are a lot of studies, which have been determined dropout problems within Nigeria and other countries as well. These studies have gone a long way to prove that dropout has been harm to many students who have gone into it. Some of the studies are stated below.

Samira (2013), conducted a study titled “Dropout syndrome among secondary schools girls”. A study of Birnin Kebbi Metropolis. The study investigated dropout syndrome among secondary school girls, the population if the study consisted of all government girls secondary schools. A proportional sampling technique was used to select 1635 respondents, self-designed questionnaire was used to collect data for the study, the questionnaire was tagged (DSSSGQ), simple percentage and tables were used to answer the four research questions generated for the study. The study found that religion background and poverty were among the causes of girl’s dropout of secondary schools. The study concluded that girls dropout from senior secondary school in Birnin Kebbi is between 20-40% and further recommended government that should develop ways of alleviating poverty in the community.

Mandina (2013) conducted a study titled “School base factor and dropout phenomenon” a study of Zhomba Cluster Secondary School in Gokwe District of Zimbabwe. The main purpose of the study was to examine school related factors and circumstances that lead to students dropping out of rural day secondary school from Zhomba cluster in Gakwe district, Zimbabwe. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A total of twenty students who had dropped out of school in the past year participated in the study. These were purposively sampled from five schools randomly chosen from nine secondary schools in the cluster. Data were collected through administering a researcher constructed 16-item likert-type questionnaire to the participants. The data obtained was compiled and analyzed using simple numbers and percentages. The study established that poverty and financial constraints were critical in the dropout phenomenon. The study also revealed that school dropout is primarily grounded in school problems such as school distance and inadequate teacher-student relationships, inadequate resources and facilities as well as an irrelevant curriculum that fails to meet the individual vocational and intellectual needs. The study therefore recommends that schools should widen and diversity their curricular to cater for students varied interest, needs and aptitudes to make school more relevant to the world of work and that parents, teachers as well as pupils should team up to work to encourage and assist children on the verge of dropping out to remain in school. Based on this previous study, the researcher found parental factors, cultural factors, school related factors, as a major reason where girls drop out of school but in this research, the researcher take a look at physical factors and educational factors as they relate to girls decision to drop out of school.

Dropout has been a problem to women participation in education and other development issue in the state. But this study will look at other factors such as psychological factor, physical factor and educational factors that that are not capture by the other researchers.

Psychological Factors Affecting Dropout in Secondary Schools:- Education is accessible only when the school is able to respond appropriately to children's learning and learning styles. Problems related to psychological factor are common feature of the educational scene in Nigeria. Govindaraju and Venkatesan (2010) discover that neglect by teachers, discrimination, negative comment meted out

by teachers be a reason of dropping out of school in rural setting in India. Croninger and Lee (2001) Lamented that positive relationship between teachers and student both in and out of class reduce the probability of dropping out by nearly half. Such a relationship is important particularly to student from disadvantage backgrounds experiences academic difficulties who are at risk of dropout. Much research have examined how teachers attitude toward female student are linked to dropout issues. Colclough, Rose and Tembon (2002) found that teachers in school more positively view boys than girls because they usually expect girls to quite school early. Teacher's attitude and their teaching practices have foremost impact sustaining girls in school. According to Nekatibeb (2002), study from several countries in sub-Saharan Africa indicate that both female and male teachers believe that boys were academically better than girls.

Research by (Fawe) Forum for African Women Educationalists (2001) shows r.it teachers were not conscious in using their language toward girls in the classroom. Mthough few researchers make the direct link, there are issues related to the observation of an appropriate teacher-student relationship and dropout. For example use of corporal punishment or violence is practiced by teachers (Boyle Brock, Mace Sibbons 2002). While it has been outlawed in some contexts, it is legal in others, though with varying degrees of restriction. Boyle, et al (2002) suggest that beating and intimidation "affect children's motivation to attend school." As a result of the tanning and accompanying humiliation students suffer at the hands of their teachers, the former gradually become less motivated to go to school. Teacher attitudes and teaching practices have important implications for the success and persistence of girls in schools. Study findings indicated that many countries reported the tendency of teachers to pay more attention to boys than girls in the classrooms. Still in other conditions boys were given priority in the distribution of books and other learning material. In many instances, teachers are not aware that the language they use in the classroom reinforces negative gender attitudes. They may use terms and expressions -and tones of voice -that give the impression that girls are not as intelligent as boys, or that girls do not need to perform well because they will just get married (FAWE, 2001).

Physical Factors Affecting Dropout in Secondary Schools:- This is also one of the courses of dropout among senior secondary schools girls. Adediran, (2008) discovered that lack of access roads to schools, and distance of communities to school is a barrier to pupil attendance, same student had to trek at least 3 Kilometers from home to school. UNICEF (2007) observed that, most schools lack adequate classroom space; furniture's and equipment are often too remotely located. Water, health and sanitation facilities are usually inadequate while student-teacher ratio could be 1:100 in urban slums. Some schools are unable to provide basic social amenities for the minimum comfort of their students. Take a look at how students defecate in the open in schools located right in the heart of the city. Their hostels are open halls without bed or beddings. In their classrooms, they are used to seat on floor without chairs to take lessons. Their meals are not even fir to sick and can be deceived into all sorts of evil things like selling their body for cash, stealing etc. This is peculiar with girls. They can get pregnant and drop out of school. In the opinion of (Glick & Sahn, 2006; Colclough, Rose and Tembon. 2000, Ainsworth, Beegle, Koda. 2005). Long distance has a strong negative impact on attending school.

Hussaini (2011) stated that lack of physical facilities is also one the major reasons of student dropping out of school, inadequate provision of physical facilities in school and poor standard of health and nutrition is one of the main causes of high dropout rate. Schools in rural areas especially remote rural areas, lack of basic facilities lack of basic facilities education and health facilities which causes student dropout and retention rate. Research points to distance to school being an important determinant of educational access. Juneja (2001) observes that in areas where schools are further away from homes, the distance may be considered too far for younger children to travel, especially young girls. This is also true in the cases of older girls and those children regarded by parents as vulnerable to sexual harassment (Colclough, Rose and Tembon 2000; Nekatibeb, 2002). Parents are afraid of the safety of their children when they have to travel longer distances to school. Thus, according to Ainsworth et al. (2005), the likelihood of children attending secondary school decreases the greater the distance to the nearest secondary school.

According to Nekatibeb (2002) distances from school has been another deterrent for girls' education in many countries in Africa. A large number of studies in the region have reported that the long distances girls travel to school has two major problems including: one related to the length of time;

and the energy children have to expend to cover the distance, often on an empty stomach, the relates to the concern and apprehension parents have for the sexual safety of their daughters. The problem of distance from school also has implications for the motivation of girls to stay in school. In Guinea, studies show that close proximity to schools had a positive motivating impact on girls; participation in schools while in Mali, most girls stated that living far away from school and having to walk discourages them. Similarly, research by Ainsworth, Beegle and Koda (2005) in Tanzania, indicate that drop outs increase in areas where distance to school is longer. In addition, illness and lack of medical care may also lead to dropout after frequent absenteeism followed by poor performance.

METHODOLOGY

Description research design is chosen because it generates answer in a statistical form which makes it easy for researchers to carry out a simple statistical analysis to interpret what the data is saying. To ensure the validity of the instrument the researcher submit to expertise in education also a pilot testing will be conducted to ensure liability of the instrument.

Research Design

This research design for this study was descriptive survey design. According to Best, (2007), the descriptive survey designed enables the researcher to obtain opinion of the representative sample of its target population. To Salaria, (2012) descriptive research is devoted in gathering information about prevailing conditions or situation for the purpose of description and interpretation and in the case of this research, it will assist in describing and interpreting the causes of dropout among senior Secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprises teachers, students and parents of three educational zones in Sokoto state that is sokoto north, sokoto south and Bodinga educational zones in Sokoto State. The composition of the population include 4837 students, 1766 teachers and parents 142 which gives the total number of 6745

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for this study will be selection from three (3) schools in Sokoto North Educational Zone, the student will be selected using sample random, sampling technique.

Data Collection

The instrument to be used for data collection is a structure questionnaire named, causes of dropout among Senior Secondary School Girls (CDSSGQ). The questionnaire contained two sections. A consist of personal data is the respondent while B consist 15 items which were divided into two section A-C.

Procedure for Data Collection

Data collection is the practical process in which a researcher goes to the field to gather information needed for the study. In this study, the researcher will use one research assistant to assist in handling the control group during the exercise. One research assistant will be used in this study because three (3) will be used for easy manageability. The research assistance will help in data collection.

Data Analysis

Data will be analyzed using mean and standard deviation in answering the research questions raised. All analysis will be done using SPSS application. For mean values below 2.5, such will be considered low while those above 2.5 will be considered high.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

Research Question One: *What are the psychological factors contribute to dropout among girls in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?*

From item statement A 1-4. This research question was answered using mean scores and standard deviation and result was presented in table 8

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviations of the Respondents on Psychological Factors contribute to Dropout among Girls in Senior Secondary Schools

S/N	Psychological Contributing Factors	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Fear of discrimination by Teachers.	2.75	1.05	Accepted
2	Lack of Parental love	2.62	1.04	Accepted
3	Teachers negative comment	2.61	.99	Accepted
4	Expulsion	2.60	1.07	Accepted
Grand Mean		2.65	1.04	Accepted

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 1 shows the mean scores and standard deviations of the respondents on psychological factors contribute to dropout among girls in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. The mean scores ranging from 2.60 to 2.75 indicated that the respondents accepted that fear of discrimination by teachers, lack of parental love, teachers negative comments and expulsion are important psychological related factors contributing to dropout among girls' in senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. The grand mean of 2.65 further showed that psychological related factors have contributed to the issue of dropout among girls in senior secondary schools in Sokoto State.

Research Question Two: *What are the physical factors contribute to dropout among girls in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?*

From item statement B 5-8. This research question was answered using mean scores and standard deviation and result was presented in table 2

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviations of the Respondents on Physical Factors Contribute to Dropout among Girls in Senior Secondary Schools

S/N	Physical Contributing Factors	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of access rounds to school	2.72	1.05	Accepted
2	School location	2.79	1.05	Accepted
3	Lack of facilities.	2.64	1.05	Accepted
4	Poor condition of infrastructure.	2.65	1.05	Accepted
Grand Mean		2.70	1.05	Accepted

Source: Field Work 2024

Table 2 shows the mean scores and standard deviations of the respondents on physical factors contribute to dropout among girls in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. The mean scores ranging from 2.64 to 2.79 indicated that the respondents accepted that lack of access rounds to school, school location, lack of facilities and poor condition of infrastructure are important psychological related factors contributing to dropout among girls' in senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. The grand mean of 2.70 further showed that physical related factors have contributed to the issue of dropout among girls in senior secondary schools in Sokoto State.

Summary of Findings

Based on the results from the analyzed data, the following are the major finding of the study

1. psychological factors contribute to dropout among girls in senior secondary schools Sokoto State, this factor are agreed by the majority of the respondents
2. Physical factors contribute to dropout among girls in senior secondary schools in to State. Where schools location serve as the major factors by the respondent.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The result generate from the eight research question were discussed as follows:-

RQ1: The data from table eight show that psychological factors contribute to dropout among girls in senior secondary school in Sokoto state with a mean score ranging from 2.60-2.75 and a grand mean of 2.65 further shows that psychological -elated factors has contributed to the issues of dropping out. The above findings is inconsistent with the findings of Govendaraju and Vencatesan (2010), who found out that neglect by teachers, discrimination, cruelty meted by teachers be the centric reasons for rapping out of school in rural schools. Though the previous study was conducted in media and most of the parents cited uncaring behavior act as a push factor to many of the students.

RQ2: Findings nine show that physical factors proved to be barriers for some students with a mean score ranging from 2.64 to 2.79 as a factors that contributed to dropout among girls in senior secondary schools in Sokoto state, with a grand mean of L~0 further shows that physical related factors contributed to the issue of dropping out. Several research studies by (Glick, 2006; Colclough, Rose & Tembo, 2000; Ainsworth, egle, & Koda 2005), discovered that long distance has a strong negative impact on attending school. The above findings was supported by Hussain (2011). who found out physical facilities and school location is also one of the major reasons for student dropping out that from school in Pakistan with respondents stating that inadequate provision of physical facilities in schools and location is one of the main causes of high dropout rate in schools in rural areas of the country.

CONCLUSIONS

The study reveals some inter-related parental, cultural, religious, economic, social, psychological, physical and educational factors that increases dropout rate and lower educational outcome of girls in general. Based on the analysis of data and interpretation of the results, the finding of this study have conclusively indicated that drop out problem has been observed to be very intricate with multiple interwoven factors responsible for leading to this complex situation. This study has made modest attempt to explore this complex situation.

1. Psychological factors contribute to dropout among girls in senior secondary school in sokoto state; reveal factors are fear of discrimination by teachers and lack of parental love extremely contribute to dropout among girls in sokoto state.
2. Physical factors accountable for dropout among girls in senior secondary school in sokoto state allied factors are school location, lack of access road to school and poor condition of infrastructure are some unique factors contribute to dropout rate among girls in sokoto state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered to help retain students in their various schools:

1. Teacher should create good relationship and friendly environment for student to feel they are at home. By so doing, it will help in controlling student emotional, phobia and psychological problems and they will feel free to speak out the fear in them; so as to feel love and appreciation again not thinking that minimal attention or feel neglected and believe teachers dislike or reject them.
2. School physical environment should be made safe, secured and at the doors of girls-children. This could be done by building more schools particularly in their locality so as to accommodate secondary school girls; and serve them from dropping out as well as long trekking from home to school.

Suggestions for Further Studies

Based on the recommendations of this study, the following suggestions are offered:-

1. A research should be conducted to know the problems of dropout girls are facing in sokoto state; to find a way forward to come to their aid.
2. A research should be conducted using other senior secondary schools in the state with a larger sample and different instrument, to ensure the instrument is reliable.
3. Another study can be conducted within or outside the state to access the variables used in this research; and to find out disparity between the two studies

4. A research should be carried out with the same objective but taking of private schools as the focus; and know if there is any disparity with public school in the state.
5. Dropout girls and the effect/ impact of socio-psychological problems in education should also be investigated.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper was funded by TETFUND under the Institutions Based Research (IBR) Annual Intervention, I therefore acknowledge their immense support. Also appreciates Shehu Shagari University of Education, Sokoto for the opportunity given to us to conduct this work.

REFERENCES

- Adediran, A. (2008). Social Problems among Nigerian women. An unpublished Dissertation submitted to the Department of Counsellors Education, University of Ilorin.
- Ajaja, P. O. (2012). School dropout pattern among senior secondary schools in Delta state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Studies*, 5(2), 145-154. Retrieved on so so date from <http://dx.doi.org/iO.5539/ies.v5n2pl45>.
- Best, j. w., & khan, j. v. (2007). Research in education. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Private.
- Boyle, S., Brock, A.; Mace J., & Sibbons, M. (2002). Reaching the Poor; The Cost of Sending Children to School, Synthesis Report, London, DFID.
- Colclough, C.: Rose, P, & Tembo, M. (2000). Gender Inequality in Primary Schooling: the Role of Poverty and Adverts cultural practices. *International Journal of Educational Development* 20 5-27. <http://dx.doi.org/10.do738-0593>
- Forum for African Women Educationalist (2001). Gender responsive School Management Systems. (Fawe) Narabi:.
- Glick, P. & Sahn, D.E. (2006). *Schooling of girls and boys in West Africa country: The effect of parental education, income and household structure*. *Economic of education review*, 19:63-87. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/so272-7757\(99\)0029-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/so272-7757(99)0029-1)
- Govindaraju, R. & Venkatesan, S. (2010). A study on school dropouts in rural settings. *Journal of Psychology*, 1(1):47-53. Retrieved 2013 <http://www.krepubfajier.com/,.goyindaraju>
- Hussain, A., Swalfi, N. A & Khan, M. T. (2011). Causes of students' dropout at primary level in Pakistan: An empirical study. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 1, (12)143-151 retrieved 2012 <http://www.ijhssnet.com>
- Juneja, N. (2001). Primary Education for all in the City of Mumbai, India; the Challenge Set by Local Actors. School Mapping and Local Level Planning Paris: UNESCO.
- National Center for Educational Statistics. (2007). *Course credit accrual and dropping out of high school*. Washington, DC: NCES 2007018
- Nekantibebe, T. (2002). Background and Rationale for School Sanitation and Hygiene Education. UNESCO institute for Capacity building in African UNESCO.
- Salaria, N. (2012). Meaning of the term description survey research method, *International Journal of Transformation in Business Management*, 1 (5), 20-32 Retrieved 2012. <http://www.ijtb.com>
- Samira, A. (20 F3). *Drop out syndrome among senior secondary schools in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis*. A Dissertation submitted to the postgraduate school, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the degree of masters of education (Educational Administration and Planning). Department of Educational Foundations.
- Samuel, T. (2w)4). *Repositioning education in Lagos state for improved service delivery: a synopsis of contending issue and policy imperator*, TESCOM News, 9 (2).
- UNICEF (2000). Country office 2007 girls education: Retrieved 2011 www.unicef.org/wcaro-nigeria-factsheet-girlseducationpdf.